

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF STAKEHOLDERS' INVOLVEMENT ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-EFFICACY AND LEARNERS' MOTIVATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 1

Pages: 37-58

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2338

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13737364

Manuscript Accepted: 07-27-2024

The Mediating Effect of Stakeholders' Involvement on the Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Learners' Motivation

Estorina B. Tugade, * Lyndon A. Quines, Geraldine D. Rodriguez

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of stakeholders' involvement on the relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation among the 228 Grade 5 learners and 120 stakeholders in 8 different schools in Maitum East District namely: Kipalkuda Elementary School, Linao Elementary School, Maitum Elementary School, Malalag Central Elementary School SPED Center, Pangi Elementary School, Sison Elementary School, Virginia Tañedo Garcia Elementary School and Wali Integrated School for the school year 2022-2023. Slovic's formula was used to calculate the learners' respondents and total enumeration for the stakeholders. Additionally, a non-experimental quantitative design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique was applied in this study. Based on the results of the study, the level of learners' self-efficacy was high in terms of student's engagement, classroom management, and instructional strategies. The level of learner's motivation was high in terms of self-motivation, intrinsic value, and cognitive strategy. The level of stakeholders' involvement was high in terms of school and budgeting, learners' participation, and implementation of school programs and reforms. Additionally, there was a significant relationship between self-efficacy and learner's motivation, self-efficacy and stakeholder's engagement, and stakeholder's engagement and learners' motivation. On the other hand, the data revealed a partial effect of self-efficacy and learners' motivation self-efficacy and stakeholders' involvement, and stakeholders' involvement and learners' motivation.

Keywords: *educational management, stakeholder's engagement, self-efficacy, learners' motivation, mediating effect, philippines*

Introduction

Students' motivation to learn, to engage actively in learning, and to persist in tricky situations while learning independently and being in the class are topics that have kept the researchers, academicians, and educators in all school levels, nationally and internationally, occupied for the past decades. Since motivation is the foundation of the learning process, educators have focused much on it over the years. Motivation is necessary for the complex and dynamic process of learning. Students take a significant step toward learning through motivation, since one of the fundamental learning components is the will to learn (Abate & Adamu, 2022).

However, students may need more willingness and interest in lessons, which put a significant barrier to effective language learning. Motivation is very diverse, one of which is motivation in learning. Implementing learning in the class generally begins with material explanations, provides sample questions, and continues with assignments. Students only listen, take notes, and do what is ordered. Teachers must expand knowledge by asking students' opinions and finding their own learning experiences (Van den Branden, 2019).

Thus, learning motivation is essential in learning activities, especially those meant to be excellent. While all students should be driven to study and perform to the best of their abilities, each learner has a different motivation. Students' motivation is reflected in their cognitive, affective, and behavioral involvement in educational activities, whether attractive or not they are for the student. The majority of motivational constructs predicted academic achievement beyond intelligence. Students' ability on self-concepts and task values are more powerful in predicting their achievement than goals and achievement motives. This is according to the few studies that have been conducted on a variety of motivational constructs as predictors of school learners' academic achievement above and beyond their cognitive abilities and prior achievement (Bartholomew et al., 2018).

On the other hand, students' learning motivation is one of the sub-factors of students' self-efficacy. Self-efficacy has been studied primarily in individual learning, and it has not been proven to hinder achievement, but rather enhance it. Thus, self-efficacy should be considered when studying motivation for learning. Learning occurs in a collaborative classroom while pupils solve problems and share results. Such an atmosphere requires teachers and learners to play roles different from those they are familiar with. Students with solid self-efficacy will take on complex tasks, show more interest, and recover if disappointed (Shin, 2018).

Undeniably, the importance of stakeholders must be addressed as they contribute significantly to various components of learners, particularly in improving their academic performance. Their pivotal role continues to be recognized by schools as they are essential for the complete development of the personality and career of the learners. More so, stakeholders significantly impact the learners' growth and development. Thus, the school and the stakeholders are responsible for leading and supporting the learners and creating an enjoyable environment to develop the latter's potential and self-confidence. In this manner, the school, in partnership with pertinent stakeholders are responsible for nurturing the learners to become responsible citizens of the world (Marks & O'Connell, 2021).

This study would like to determine the stakeholders' involvement related to context variables in the given scenario. It will examine the relationship between the stakeholders' involvement and its mediating effect on self-efficacy and learners' motivation. With these

pronouncements, a deeper understanding of stakeholders' involvement in the learners' academic performance is necessary. The results could provide specific participation associated with stakeholders' involvement. They may contribute further to the partnership between the stakeholders and schools as one decisive factor for the success of DepEd's educational reforms and school-initiated activities.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of the stakeholders' involvement on the relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation of Grade 5 learners in East Maitum District for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it achieved the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the level of self-efficacy of learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. student's engagement;
 - 1.2. classroom management, and
 - 1.3. instructional strategies.
2. To determine the level of learners' motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1 self-motivation;
 - 2.2 intrinsic value; and
 - 2.3 cognitive strategy
3. To determine the level of stakeholders' involvement in terms of:
 - 3.1 school planning and budgeting;
 - 3.2 learners' participation; and
 - 3.3 implementation of school programs and reforms.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1 self-efficacy and learners' motivation;
 - 4.2 self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement;
 - 4.3 stakeholders' engagement and learners' motivation
5. To determine the significance of mediation of stakeholders' involvement in the relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation.

Methodology

This section presents the research design, locale, population and sample, and a comprehensive research instrument and data collection process. These elements, along with the statistical tools and ethical considerations, form a robust framework guiding every aspect of the reflection.

Research Design

This meticulously crafted non-experimental quantitative study design, with its unique use of the descriptive correlation technique is a testament to the thoroughness of this research. The use of a quantitative research strategy, defined by a quantitative research design, underscores the commitment to a scientific approach. The careful collection of data, concepts, facts, and information relevant to the investigation without manipulating or controlling the variables ensures high accuracy and reliability in the data collection process (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019).

This strategy seeks to quantify the prevalence of a given opinion, action, or feeling, and its use of large sample sizes emphasize the volume of replies. Respondents to a quantitative research design are often asked identical questions, allowing for a thorough analysis of the entire data sample. Additionally, the data are provided numerically, enabling statistical analysis in quantitative form (Rahman, 2020).

Moreover, closed-ended questions are often favored in quantitative research. Generally, the respondents can only deliver detailed, open-ended answers if they supply them with a predetermined list of possibilities. Compared to the case of using an open-ended qualitative research question, this design ensures that the quantitative research procedure is far more effective. It is more efficient because it eliminates the necessity of coding a significant portion of open-ended responses, which is laborious. Nonetheless, the quantitative research design typically permits the addition of an "Other" category in the list of potential responses to questions when it is suitable. Because of this, correct replies from the respondents who do not precisely fit into the main categories can still be collected and the used to assess the research findings (Swart et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the quantitative research design aims to gather and generalize numerical data to various populations. Every detail in this design is painstakingly and precisely prepared, instilling confidence in the thoroughness and validity of the study. The researcher has a clearly stated research question to which objective solutions are sought. Data examples include statistics and numerical data. A project can be used to look into causal linkages, forecast results, or generalize ideas more broadly (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

On the other hand, research methodology, known as a correlational study, looks at the connections between two or more variables. A non-experimental research method known as correlational analysis allows researchers to measure two variables, comprehend and assess

their statistical relationship, and do so without the influence of any other variable. No variables are altered or subject to the experimenter's control because correlational studies are not experimenting (Seeram, 2019).

Similarly, if determining the influence or relationship between the variables is the main objective of a study, then the descriptive-correlational research approach is the most appropriate. In this study, the main objective was to ascertain whether there was a connection between parental participation, work satisfaction, and the learners' academic progress, hence the use of a quantitative technique is preferable. Moreover, quantitative research designs often exhibit a deterministic philosophy based on the post-positivist paradigm or school of thought. Post-positivists investigate causes and the interactions and effects of various causes on outcomes. The post-positivist paradigm embraces the idea that reality can be discovered, albeit imperfectly and in a probabilistic sense. The approach is typically deductive, where most ideas or concepts are reduced to variables, and the relationship between or among them is tested. The results are based on meticulous observation, measurement, and interpretation of objective reality (Siedlecki, 2020).

Furthermore, the descriptive-correlation research design explains and analyzes the world around us, shedding light on genuine and imagined relationships and situations. Additionally, because it is a fact-finding study, the researcher can look at the study participants' traits, actions, and experiences. It is correlational since it investigated the relationship between variables such as learner's behavior, teaching performance, and job satisfaction, using the survey questionnaire to gather the primary data. The interest of the study is to investigate the relationship between school-initiated activities and learners' academic performance, the relationship between school-initiated activities and stakeholders' involvement, the relationship between learners' academic performance and stakeholders' involvement, and the mediating effect of stakeholders' involvement on the relationship between school-initiated activities and learners' academic performance in Maitum East District. Path Analysis was employed to determine the mediation.

Participants

There are 228 Grade 5 learners and 120 stakeholders of Maitum East District. There were 62 learners and 15 stakeholders from Kipalkuda Elementary School, 38 learners and 15 stakeholders from Linao Elementary School, 58 learners and 25 stakeholders from Maitum Elementary School. There were 189 learners and 15 stakeholders from Malalag Elementary School. 38 learners and 15 stakeholders from Pangi Elementary School. 45 learners and 19 stakeholders from Sison Elementary School. 36 learners and 15 stakeholders from VTG Elementary School, and 64 learners and 28 stakeholders from Wali Integrated School.

The researcher utilized Slovin's Formula to obtain the desired sample of learners. The final number of respondents was 228 out of 530 Grade 5 learners. Total enumeration was employed to gather the population of stakeholders. The Slovin formula determined the appropriate sample size needed to obtain a representative sample, given the population size and desired level of precision or margin of error. The formula is: $n = N / (1 + N(e^2))$ (Adhikari, 2021).

On the other hand, total enumeration refers to a research method in which the data are gathered from an entire population rather than a sample to represent the population accurately. This method is beneficial when the population is small and manageable. It eliminates the possibility of sampling error, but can be time-consuming and costly (Ismail et al., 2022). Moreover, the table presents the distribution of participants in the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

School	Number of Respondents		
	Learners		Stakeholders
	N	N	
Kipalkuda Elementary School	62	27	15
Linao Elementary School	38	17	15
Maitum Elementary School	50	25	15
Malalag, Central ES SPED Center	189	81	15
Pangi Elementary School	38	16	15
Sison Elementary School	45	19	15
VTG Elementary School	36	16	15
Wali Integrated School	64	28	15
Total	530	228	120

Inclusion Criteria. The researcher applied a total enumeration to get the desired population of the teacher respondents, while Slovin's formula was utilized to get the population of learners. The research focused on teachers and learners from five different schools in the Municipality of Maitum, Sarangani Province. Additionally, specific requirements were established for both learners and teachers to ensure that the participants met the inclusion criteria. For the learners, inclusion criteria included being male or female, residing within Sarangani Province, and being a student in one of the eight selected schools. Similarly, specific requirements were put in place for the teachers. The inclusion criteria for teachers involved being male or female, residing within Sarangani Province, holding a degree in education, meeting the qualifications of a professional teacher, and currently employed in one of the eight schools in Maitum.

Exclusion Criteria. This study explicitly targets learners and teachers within eight different schools in the Municipality of Maitum, Sarangani Province. Consequently, respondents who are not assigned to these particular areas were not included in the research sample to ensure the relevance and specificity of the findings. Regarding the teacher respondents, the study concentrated to those teaching for

at least three years within the specified areas. Additionally, teachers above 25 and under 60 were considered for inclusion. Retired teachers were not part of the study population as the focus was on actively employed teachers within the target schools. For learner participants, the study exclusively focused on students enrolled in the eight different schools chosen for the research. The research sample did not include learners not attending in these specific schools.

Withdrawal Criteria. Throughout the study, respondents were reminded of their ability to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any repercussions. Thus, it ensured that the respondents knew precisely their rights and could quickly stop participating if it made them uncomfortable. They did not need to give a reason for leaving.

Instruments

Three questionnaires were adapted from different authors and used in this study.

Questionnaire for Stakeholders' Involvement. A questionnaire was used to determine the level of stakeholders' involvement. It was a researcher-made questionnaire with three indicators: school planning and budgeting, learner participation, and implementation of school programs and reforms. Each indicator has five statements.

Questionnaire for Self-efficacy. A questionnaire was used to determine the level of stakeholders' involvement. It was adapted and modified from the Teachers' Sense of Efficacy: A Challenge for Professional Development toward Teaching Science as Inquiry by Seneviratne et al. (N/A). It has three indicators: students' engagement with six statements, classroom management with five statements, and instructional strategies with five statements.

Questionnaire for Learners' Motivation. A questionnaire was used to determine the level of learners' motivation. It was adapted and modified from the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) coined by Pintrich and De Groot (1990). The questionnaire has three indicators: self-motivation has nine statements; intrinsic value has nine statements; and cognitive strategy, which has 12 statements.

Data Collection

The data for this study were collected based on the book "Fundamentals of Research Methodology and Data Collection" by Igwenagu (2016). To conduct the study, the researcher had to fulfill specific responsibilities, including approaching the organization and seeking permission. The researcher ensured compliance with any specific research activity policies established by the organization, following the necessary steps to uphold the ethical and valid nature of the study.

To begin with, the researcher developed research questions that were then validated by a designated validator. This step was crucial in ensuring the clarity and appropriateness of the research questions. Once the research questions were validated, the researcher sought approval from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) to guarantee that the study would be conducted ethically, with the well-being and rights of the participants as a top priority.

Having obtained approval from the Ethics Research Committee, the researcher obtained permission from the Dean of their institution and the Schools Division Superintendent of Sarangani Province. This additional step aimed to establish a formal endorsement and recognition of the study within the academic and educational authorities. This is to solidify the legitimacy and support for the research endeavor.

Once permission was granted, the researcher requested the participation of individuals willing to participate in the study and provided them with an Informed Consent Form. The researcher distributed the questionnaires and became ready to respond immediately to any queries the respondents had if they approved and agreed to participate in the study. There was an ample time for the instructor respondents to finish the questionnaire. The researcher addressed any queries about the study. The researcher then collected the results, combined them, and used statistical analysis after obtaining the data from the questionnaires.

After retrieving the questionnaires from the teachers, the researcher requested a copy of the learners' grades for Quarter 2. After interpreting the data gathered, the researcher continued developing programs as interventions, given the study's results.

Ethical Considerations

For this quantitative study, a critical ethical factor has specific ramifications. These problems and worries can primarily result from the approach used in this study. The ethical considerations in this research were concerned with the proper conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration were adhered to in this study, especially when it came to the population and data, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were granted permission to participate without expecting consequences, payment, or loss of benefits. Therefore, after discussing the study's purpose and benefits, the participant's rights to provide the body of knowledge were carefully measured and foresighted. The subjects in this study were not coerced into taking part. If people get uncomfortable while participating in the study, they can stop.

Privacy and confidentiality. By the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the respondents have a right to privacy that should not be infringed upon

without their consent. This act safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy. Allowing the respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. Additionally, secrecy and privacy were achieved by withholding the informants' demographic information, such as age, gender, occupation, and medical condition. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons. Their answers to the survey questionnaire were kept private and treated as such.

Informed consent process. The prospective research respondents were fully informed about the research's objectives, methods, and benefits as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. The respondents' written consent was obtained, indicating their participation was asked voluntarily. The respondents signed the informed consent form stating they willingly consented to participate in the study. Since the respondents were consenting adults, asking for parents' consent was unnecessary. The respondents' identities were not mentioned on the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The participants knew they could withdraw from participating in the study at any time.

Furthermore, any data the researcher gathered were protected, and releasing any information would follow a strict informed consent process. The participants would control their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information would be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. For the respondents to understand the study, the researcher explained its purpose for further inference and understanding of its essence. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the purpose and importance of the study.

Risks. If the benefit-risk ratio is acceptable and positive, research will be done. This study's need to protect the participants from significant harm is equally essential. Therefore, the study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern as the researcher needed to ensure that the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. The researcher answered the survey questionnaire and confirmed that the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. This study would benefit the respondents it offers a foundation for understanding how stakeholders' engagement impacts the interplay between educators' self-efficacy and learners' motivation. Furthermore, the student outcomes can inform school division Superintendents in tailoring supplementary programs to address learners' behavior, enhance teaching efficacy, and foster job satisfaction among educators. School Heads can leverage these findings to develop targeted initiatives that bolster learner motivation through tailored school activities. Therefore, this study has been conducted to help teachers, stakeholders, especially learners. Furthermore, to achieve beneficence in research, the researcher did all the aspects that would not harm the respondents' lives and thus would benefit the further undertakings of the related studies. The most essential to achieving benefits is the rise of meaningful learning.

Plagiarism. The study was run via plagiarism detection tools such as Grammarly, and it had no traces or indications of misinterpreting someone else's work. Cheerful character and integrity, linked to moral characteristics and ideals, are essential for researchers. The researcher must know more about plagiarism to produce a trustworthy research report.

Fabrication. The report did not hint or provide evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. Instead, the investigator utilized and combined information-related ideas with additional inferential notions.

Falsification. There was no indication that the study overstated or exaggerated anything, nor did it deliberately falsify the data to meet a model or theoretical expectation. Furthermore, this study did not follow data manipulation protocols, which entailed making claims based on incomplete information, omitting crucial aspects, or using materials, instruments, or techniques in a way that would deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study had no trace of conflicts of interest, such as the disclosure of COI, which is a collection of circumstances under which professional judgment regarding primary claims like respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. Furthermore, the respondents were not coerced by the researcher into participating in the survey she has no authority over them.

Deceit. There was no evidence that the study misled the respondents about potential risks. The rights of everybody who participated in an investigation were fiercely protected, especially if they had completed higher education. Therefore, reasonable and suitable standards must be followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher of this study followed protocols. Upon receiving the signal from the panelists, adviser, and committee of the RMMCERC, the researcher sought approval from the school's division superintendent to conduct the study through a formal letter. After this, with the approval of the School's Division Superintendent, the researcher wrote an official letter to the study's district supervisor and principal of the participating schools. The public elementary school teachers who were part of the study were oriented before administering the survey questionnaire.

Technology Issues. To disseminate the information, the researcher uses technology, especially for the hard-to-reach respondents. Using

online survey research may be very important in gathering responses and collecting survey results into one data set ready for analysis. By utilizing technology, it is easy to collect the findings of the intended respondents using an online survey questionnaire; provisions for online panels, data collection online, and how one interprets information being communicated in an online environment are also put in place and made clear to the participants.

Authorship. Lastly, this study considers authorship qualifications. The researcher credits all the people who contributed to the successful publication of the study, especially the research adviser, the statistician, the school head and school principal, and the panelists who made substantial contributions to the study leading to its publication.

Results

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data in the study.

3.1. The Level of Self-Efficacy of Learners

Table 2 presents data on learners' self-efficacy in various aspects of their academic life, including school planning and budgeting, learners' participation, and implementation of school programs and reforms. The data provide insights into the students' confidence in these areas, which can significantly impact their academic success.

According to the data, learners exhibited a high level of self-efficacy, as indicated by a mean score of 4.3. This mean score is significantly higher than the midpoint of 3, which suggests that the learners were actively engaged in the classroom, emphasizing the importance of improving their class participation through fostering creativity, valuing learning, and promoting a belief in themselves. A mean score of 4.3 indicates a high level of self-efficacy, which is a positive sign for students' engagement and learning outcomes. They demonstrated a strong inclination towards critical thinking, displaying motivation to show interest in the class, and maintaining a belief in their ability to succeed. This finding highlights the positive impact of self-efficacy on students' engagement and suggests that nurturing self-belief and motivation can contribute to enhanced learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the data reveal that the learners demonstrated a commendable level of self-efficacy in classroom management, as evidenced by a mean score of 3.9. This high self-efficacy indicates that the learners can establish and maintain classroom management styles that contribute to a calm and smooth learning environment. They proactively clarify expectations, adhere to classroom rules, and implement routines to ensure organized activities. This finding reassures the educators about students' ability to create a conducive learning atmosphere, positively impacting their learning experience and academic success.

Similarly, the data indicate that the learners exhibited a high level of self-efficacy in instructional strategies, as indicated by a mean score of 4.1. This high self-efficacy suggests that the learners have developed robust learning skills, enabling them to effectively tackle challenging questions, evaluate their understanding of the teacher's instruction, and employ diverse learning strategies. They actively seek clarification from teachers by requesting alternative examples when faced with confusion, fostering a growth mindset and a willingness to explore different approaches to learning. Moreover, learners can generate thoughtful and practical questions, indicating their critical thinking and problem-solving proficiency. This high level of self-efficacy in instructional strategies underscore the learners' confidence and competence in navigating complex learning tasks. Educators should instill confidence in the student's academic progress and achievement.

Overall, the data indicate that the learners exhibit high level of self-efficacy across various dimensions. They actively engage in the classroom, emphasizing the importance of nurturing creativity, valuing learning, and promoting self-belief. The learners also demonstrate strong self-efficacy in classroom management, contributing to a calm and organized learning environment. Also, their proficiency in instructional strategies highlight robust learning skills, a growth mindset, and practical problem-solving abilities. Thus, fostering and nurturing self-belief and motivation among the learners can significantly improve class participation, create a positive learning atmosphere, and enhance academic progress.

Table 2. *The Level of Learner's Self-Efficacy*

<i>A. Students Engagement The learners in our school</i>		<i>Mean n-228</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. think critically		4.1	High
2. feel motivated to show interest in the class		4.4	High
3. believe they can do well		4.6	Very High
4. value learning		3.9	High
5. Foster creativity		3.9	High
6. Improving the class participation.		4.3	High
Total		4.3	High
<i>B. Classroom Management The Learners in out school</i>			
1. Make expectations clear		4.4	High
2. Establish routines to keep activities smooth		3.5	High
3. Follow classroom rules.		3.8	High

4. Is calm	3.4	Moderately High
5. Establish classroom management styles.	4.6	Very High
Total	3.9	High
<i>C. Instructional Strategies</i>		
<i>The learners in our school</i>		
1. Respond to difficult questions		
2. Assess comprehension based on what the teacher has taught	4.1	High
3. Use a variety of learning strategies	4.4	High
4. ask for alternative examples from teachers when they get confused	3.3	High
5. can craft good questions	4.4	High
TOTAL	4.1	High

3.2. The Level of Learners' Motivation

Table 3 presents the data on the level of learners' motivation in terms of self-motivation, intrinsic value, and cognitive strategy. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Moreover, the data reveal that the learners displayed a high level of motivation, particularly in self-motivation, as evidenced by a mean score of 3.9. This high self-motivation suggests that the learners are committed to fostering positive self-belief and confidence in their abilities to excel in project work and succeed in their studies. The learners acknowledge their strengths, unique talents, and skills and are motivated and committed to learn the material. They hold high expectations of their performance compared to their peers, demonstrate a solid understanding of the presented ideas, and are enthusiastic to learn and showcase their abilities. This high level of self-motivation should encourage educators to be aware of the student's commitment to learning and their potential for academic success.

Moreover, data reveal that the learners exhibited a high level of motivation in terms of intrinsic value, as indicated by a mean score of 3.9, thus suggesting agreement among the learners regarding their positive attitude towards learning and their embrace of challenging project work. They are driven to learn and comprehend the concepts, finding the content engaging and meaningful. The learners recognize the practical value of the skills and knowledge being taught and are committed to expand their knowledge base. Furthermore, they view mistakes as valuable learning opportunities and are motivated to improve continuously. The learners express enthusiasm in applying what they have learned to future endeavors and prioritize understanding the topic for personal and professional growth. This high intrinsic motivation demonstrates the learners' genuine interest in the subject matter and desire to grow and develop through their educational experiences.

Furthermore, data reveal that the learners exhibited a high level of motivation in cognitive strategy. This term refers to students' mental processes and techniques to understand and remember information. A mean score of 3.9 indicates agreement among the learners regarding their focus on employing various cognitive strategies and techniques to enhance their learning and comprehension of project work. The learners actively engage in strategies such as integrating information from diverse sources, identifying main ideas and critical concepts, paraphrasing essential information, and leveraging prior knowledge and experiences to tackle new assignments. They employ techniques such as recalling information shared by project members, utilizing rote memorization, rewriting notes, repetition, and establishing connections between new information and previously acquired knowledge. The goal is to facilitate effective memory retention, improve understanding, and foster a deeper understanding of complex topics. This high level of motivation in employing cognitive strategies underscore the learners' commitment to active learning and their drive to develop effective learning techniques that optimize their academic performance and overall understanding of the subject matter.

Table 3. *The Level of Learners' Motivation*

	<i>Self-Motivation</i>	<i>Mean n=228</i>	<i>Description</i>
In school....			
1. confident in abilities and expect to perform well compared to peers in the class.		3.5	High
2. students believe in comprehending the ideas presented in the project work and are excited to learn more.		4.4	High
3. have faith and expect to excel in this study system.		4.7	Very High
4. Recognize strengths as a student and feel confident in the abilities to succeed. 5. excel in completing the problems and tasks assigned for this project.		3.6	High
5. excel in completing the problems and tasks assigned for this project.		3.8	High
6. Be confident in exerting effort and dedication to this project, and believe in receiving an excellent grade.		3.6	High
7. the acknowledgment of the unique talents and skills and excited to showcase them in this class.		4.1	High
8. knowledgeable about the subject and feel the edge compared to other students. 9. motivated and committed to learning the material for this project, and know the will to succeed.		4.0	High
9. motivated and committed to learning the material for this project, and know the will to		3.0	High

succeed.		
Total	3.9	High
<i>Intrinsic Value</i>		
In school.....		
1. motivated by the opportunity to learn and grow through challenging project work.	3.6	High
2. driven to learn and understand the concepts presented in the project work.	3.9	High
3. find the content of the projects engaging and enjoyable to learn.	4.5	Very High
4. excited to apply the knowledge and skills gained from this project in future endeavors.	4.1	High
5. committed to learning and expanding the knowledge, even if it requires additional effort and time.	4.0	High
6. view mistakes as an opportunity to learn, improve, and understand the material.	4.1	High
7. recognize the practical value of the concepts and skills taught in this class and are eager to incorporate them into life.	3.5	High
8. be fascinated by the topics this class covers and find them exciting and engaging.	3.5	High
9. Placing a high value on understanding this topic, believing it will benefit personal and professional growth.	3.9	High
TOTAL	3.8	High
<i>Cognitive Strategy</i>		
In school.....		
1. To prepare for assessments, integrate information from various sources, including the project and other resources.	3.6	High
2. employ the technique of recalling information shared by other project members to facilitate work when working independently.	4.3	High
3. employ a strategy of identifying the main ideas and key concepts in what it read to facilitate understanding.	4.7	Very High
4. use the cognitive strategy of paraphrasing important information in one's own words to facilitate comprehension and memory retention.	3.6	High
6. Use rote memorization to retain essential facts when preparing for assessments.	3.8	High
7. employ the technique of rewriting notes to reinforce memory and comprehension of the material.	3.6	High
8. use the cognitive strategy of active listening and attempting to understand even when the material is initially confusing.	4.0	High
9. use the cognitive strategy of applying previous knowledge and experience to new assignments to facilitate learning.	3.5	High
10. use a cognitive strategy of organizing and synthesizing information to facilitate understanding of complex topics.	3.5	High
11. employ the technique of repetition to reinforce memory and comprehension of important Information.	4.1	High
12. use a cognitive strategy of connecting new information and previously acquired knowledge to facilitate comprehension and retention of new material.	4.0	High
Total	3.8	High

3.3. The Level of Stakeholders’ Involvement

Table 4 presents the data on stakeholders’ involvement in school planning and budgeting, learners’ participation, and implementation of school programs and reforms. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

According to the data, the stakeholders demonstrated a high level of involvement in school planning and budgeting, as indicated by a mean score of 3.7, which suggests agreement among the stakeholders regarding their active participation in crafting a School Improvement Plan (SIP) and an Annual Implementation Budget to align in school programs and activities. The input and ideas of the stakeholders are sought during the planning process, ensuring that diverse perspectives and insights are considered. Additionally, efforts are made to secure funding for school-initiated projects by engaging private sponsors. A comprehensive three-year program is devised to ensure proper funding and seamless implementation. The primary focus is effectively utilizing and implementing the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) fund to support the school initiatives. A high level of stakeholders’ involvement underscores their commitment to collaborative decision-making and their dedication to optimizing resource allocation for the betterment of the school and its programs.

Likewise, the stakeholders demonstrated a high level of involvement in promoting learners’ participation, as indicated by a mean score of 3.8. The stakeholders agree regarding their focus on supporting the learners' engagement in various programs and activities and providing incentives for high-performing students. The stakeholders prioritize motivating the learners to enhance their academic

performance, offering support, and monitoring progress through teachers’ feedback. The overarching goal is to foster harmonious relationships among the teachers, students, and stakeholders, creating a collaborative and supportive learning environment. This high level of stakeholders’ involvement highlights their commitment to the empowering learners and nurturing their holistic development, ensuring they receive the necessary support, recognition, and encouragement to thrive academically and actively participate in school programs and activities.

Furthermore, the stakeholders exhibited a high level of involvement in implementing school programs and reforms, as indicated by a mean score of 3.8, which suggests agreement among the stakeholders regarding their active engagement in ensuring the successful execution of school programs through their involvement. The stakeholders take on tasks such as monitoring programs and projects and organizing a comprehensive plan for their implementation. The primary focus is ensuring the learners’ benefit from school-initiated programs and projects. Additionally, the stakeholders prioritize harmonization and transparency in implementing programs and reforms to create an environment where all of them can actively contribute and participate. This high stakeholders’ involvement underscores their dedication to effectively execute school initiatives, resulting in enhanced educational experiences and positive outcomes for the learners and the entire school community.

Table 4. *The Level of Stakeholders' Involvement*

<i>School Planning and Budgeting</i>	<i>Mean n=120</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>The Stakeholders in our school</i>		
1. involved in crafting of School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Budget to align school programs and activities.	3.5	High
2. solicit ideas for school planning and project implementation.	3.7	High
3. tap private sponsors to provide funding for the school-initiated project.	4.1	High
4. plan for a three-year program in the school to align proper funding and implementation.	3.5	High
5. ensure that the MOOE fund will be utilized appropriately and implemented	3.8	High
TOTAL	3.7	High
<i>Learner's Participation</i>		
<i>The Stakeholders in our school</i>		
1. support learners' participation in different programs and activities	3.7	High
2. provide incentives for performing students	3.5	High
3. motivate learners to improve their academic performance through stakeholder support	3.7	High
4. monitor student progress through teacher's feedback	4.1	High
5. ensure harmonious relationships with teachers, students, and stakeholders	4.0	High
TOTAL	3.8	High
<i>Implementation of School Programs and Reforms</i>		
<i>The Stakeholders in our school</i>		
1. ensure that the implementation of school programs will be successfully done through their involvement	3.6	High
2. monitor the school-initiated programs and projects	3.5	High
3. organize a plan for the implementation of school programs and reforms	4.1	High
4. ensure that learners will benefit from the school-initiated programs and projects	4.1	High
5. guarantee that the school programs and reforms are harmonized and transparent	3.6	High
TOTAL	3.8	High

3.4. Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Learners’ Motivation

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between self-efficacy and learners’ motivation. In collecting the data, Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed.

It was found that when the level of self-efficacy and the level of learners’ motivation were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 226. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value, as indicated in the table was 0.148. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.75, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The level of self-efficacy significantly influenced the level of the learners’ motivation.

Table 5. *Significant Relationships between Self-efficacy and Learner's Motivation*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>rx_y value</i>		<i>Decision</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
		<i>Comoputed</i>	<i>Tabluar</i>		
Self-Efficacy vs. Learner's Motivation	226	0.75	0.148	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.5. Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Stakeholders’ Involvement

Table 6 presents the significant relationship between self-efficacy and stakeholders’ involvement. The data were gathered using Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation.

It was found that when the level of self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 226. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value, as indicated in the table was 0.148. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.79, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The level of self-efficacy significantly influenced the level of stakeholders' engagement.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Stakeholder Involvement*

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value		Decision	Analysis
		Comoputed	Tabluar		
Self-Efficacy vs. Learner's Motivation	118	0.79	0.148	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.6. Significant Relationship Between Stakeholder's Involvement and Learner's Motivation

Table 7 presents the significant relationship between the stakeholders' involvement and learners' motivation. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to gather the data.

It was found that when the level of stakeholders' involvement and the level of learner's motivation were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 226. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value, as indicated in the table was 0.148. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.81, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, the stakeholders' engagement level significantly influenced the learner's motivation. These findings underscore the importance of the stakeholders' involvement in shaping and sustaining learners' motivation, emphasizing the interconnectedness of these factors in the educational context.

Table 7. *Significant Relationships between Stakeholders Involvement and Learners Motivation*

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value		Decision	Analysis
		Comoputed	Tabluar		
Stakeholders Involvement vs Learner's Motivation	346	0.81	0.148	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.7. On the Mediating Effect of Stakeholders, Engagement on the Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Learners' Motivation

Table 8 presents the path analysis of the mediating effect of the stakeholders' engagement on the relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation.

The data revealed the direct effect of self-efficacy on learners' motivation, and stakeholders' involvement. The routes with an unstandardized regression coefficient of .899 and a standardized regression coefficient of .820, S.E. were self-efficacy and learners' motivation. .044, as well as a probability value that is smaller than 0.05. A low or tiny standard error indicates that the estimate is more accurate, and below the significance level of 0.05 suggests that these two variables have a meaningful relationship. The effect size or the impact of efficiency is 95%, which is large enough to reject the null hypothesis.

Moreover, the path b coefficient, which is self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .089, a standardized regression coefficient of .124, an S.E. of .031, and a p-value of .019, which is smaller than the significance alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the relationship between self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement is significant. The effect size of teacher's work-life satisfaction and self-esteem is 10%.

Lastly, the path c coefficient presents the effect size of stakeholder's engagement and learners' motivation. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .658 or 79% efficiency, a standardized regression coefficient of .658, a computed standard error of .841, and a p-value smaller than 0.50, meaning the two variables have a significant relationship. Mathematically, this supports the assumption that the stakeholders' engagement is associated with learners' motivation.

Table 8. *Mediating Effect Path Analysis (Partial Mediator)*

Path	Estimates				
	Unstandardized	Standardized	SE	C.R.	P
Self-Efficacy Learner's Motivation	.899	.820	.044	29.142	***
Self-Efficacy Stakeholder's Involvement	.089	.124	.031	2.523	.019
Stakeholder's Involvement Learner's Motivation	.658	.841	.050	14.544	***

Figure 3. Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect of Stakeholder's Involvement on the Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Learner's Motivation

Discussion

This section highlights the essential findings and presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the data gathered.

The Level of Self-Efficacy

The level of learners' self-efficacy was high, particularly in student engagement. Encouraging findings indicate that learners actively improve class participation by fostering creativity, valuing learning, and promoting a belief in themselves. Students are encouraged to think critically, feel motivated to show interest in the class, and believe in their ability to do well. It aligns with the study of Barni et al. (2019), who suggest that teachers can foster students' engagement through various techniques, such as active learning strategies, project-based learning, and technology-enhanced instruction. Creating a positive, encouraging classroom climate where students feel free to share their thoughts and ask questions and provide them with opportunities for autonomy and choice in their learning can further increase their motivation and ownership over their education.

Moreover, the level of learners' self-efficacy in classroom management indicates that the learners establish classroom management styles that promote a calm and smooth learning environment. Learners are encouraged to clarify expectations, follow classroom rules, and establish routines to keep the activities organized. This assumption parallels to the study of Franklin and Harrington (2019), who claim that effective classroom management is vital for addressing various children's demands, including their academic strengths and challenges, cultural backgrounds, and personal interests. To do this, teachers must identify and respond to individual student needs, which requires careful planning, attention to detail, and a commitment to continuous development. Effective classroom management strategies help create a positive learning environment that promotes student engagement, academic achievement, and overall well-being by establishing clear expectations, building positive relationships, and meeting the diverse needs of students.

Further, the level of learners' self-efficacy regarding instructional strategies was high, indicating that the learners developed strong learning skills that enabled them to respond to difficult questions, assess their comprehension of what the teacher has taught, and use various learning strategies. Students are encouraged to ask for alternative examples from teachers when confused and to develop the ability to craft good questions. This assumption parallels to the study of Vong and Kaewurai (2017), who claim that instructional strategies are tailored to meet diverse learners' needs. For example, differentiated instruction teachers can better meet the needs of students with varying levels of prior knowledge, interests, and learning styles. Thus, helps to ensure that all students have the opportunity to succeed academically.

The Level of Learners' Motivation

The level of learners' motivation was high in terms of self-motivation, indicating that the learners' focus is on a positive self-belief and confidence in one's abilities to excel in the project work and succeed in the study system. The students acknowledge their strengths, unique talents, and skills and they are motivated and committed to learn the material. The students expect to perform well compared to peers, comprehend the ideas presented, and they are excited to learn and showcase their abilities. The students are confident in their effort and dedication and expects to receive an excellent grade. This assumption parallels to the study of Gonzalez-DeHass (2019), who claims that cultivating self-motivation can help identify one's values and priorities, set realistic goals that align with those values, and break those goals down into smaller, manageable steps. It can also be helpful to execute positive self-talk, visualize success, and reward oneself for progress. Additionally, staying curious, seeking out new experiences and challenges, and maintaining a growth mindset can all contribute to a strong sense of self-motivation.

In addition, the level of the learners' motivation was high in terms of intrinsic value, indicating agreement that the learners' focus is on a positive attitude toward learning and growth through challenging project work. The student are driven to learn and understand the concepts, find the content engaging, and see the practical value of the skills and knowledge taught. They are committed to expanding their knowledge and view problems as opportunities to learn and develop. The students are excited to apply what they have learned in future endeavors and value understanding the topic for personal and professional growth. This assumption parallels to the study of Fithriani (2021), who claims that motivated learners consider learning activities meaningful and valuable and try to gain from them. It is the defining factor that affects the achievement of a specific goal and the learning behavior that continues until the goal is achieved. In general, motivation refers to the reason for a specific action; it has the characteristics of inducing certain behaviors, presenting a sense of direction, and continuing it. In other words, it is the power to initiate action, determine direction, and determine the persistence and intensity of action.

Moreover, Adams et al. (2019) claim that intrinsic values play a significant role in online learning environments. They are associated with increased engagement and successful course completion. The study revealed that learners driven by intrinsic values, such as a genuine desire for self-improvement and a love for learning, were likelier to participate in online learning activities and complete online courses actively.

The Level of Stakeholders' Involvement

The level of stakeholders' involvement was high in school planning and budgeting, which means that the stakeholders are involved in crafting a School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Budget to align in school programs and activities. Ideas for school planning and project implementation are solicited, and private sponsors are tapped to fund the school-initiated project. A three-year program is planned to align proper funding and implementation. The focus is on ensuring the proper utilization and implementation of the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) fund, a specific fund allocated for the school's day-to-day operations. This assumption parallels to the study of Lai et al. (2022), who claim that cognitive strategies play a crucial role in decision-making by enabling individuals to make sound and rational choices. Various cognitive strategies can be applied in decision-making, including evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of different options, assessing the potential outcomes of each option, and seeking further information to support the decision-making process.

Likewise, the level of stakeholders' involvement was high, which means that the stakeholders' focus is on supporting learners' participation in different programs and activities and providing incentives for high-performing students. There is an emphasis on motivating the learners to improve their academic performance through the stakeholders' support and monitoring students' progress through teacher feedback. The aim is to ensure harmonious relationships with the teachers, students, and stakeholders. This assumption parallels to the study of Kujala et al. (2022), who claim that the stakeholder involvement has various meanings and uses in the literature. A common focus of stakeholders' involvement is the differing interests between the companies and the stakeholders' group, to the extent that stakeholders' theory is assumed to be 'about managing potential conflict stemming from divergent interests.

Additionally, the stakeholders' involvement was high in implementing school programs and reforms, indicating that they are involved in ensuring the successful implementation of school programs through monitoring programs and projects, and organizing a plan for their implementation. The focus is ensuring that learners benefit from school-initiated programs and projects and that the programs and reforms are harmonized and transparent. This assumption parallels to the study of Marshal (2018), who claims that school planning and budgeting require the involvement of the stakeholders to ensure that the school's goals and objectives are aligned to the needs and expectations of the community.

Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Learners' Motivation

Data reveal a significant relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation. It implies that self-efficacy is associated with the learners' motivation. It was found that when the level of self-efficacy and the level of learner's motivation were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a pdf of 226. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value, as indicated in the table was 0.148. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.75. Thus, it may lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The level of self-efficacy significantly influenced the level of the learner's motivation.

This assumption parallels to the study of Adegoke et al. (2021), who claim that there is indeed a significant relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in his/hetr ability to accomplish specific tasks or goals. It is a psychological construct determining how individuals approach and engage in learning activities. Conversely, "motivation" describes the internal or external forces that propel people to start and maintain particular activities, such as learning. Various factors, including self-beliefs, goals, interests, and expectations can influence motivation.

Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Stakeholder Engagement

Data revealed a significant relationship between self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement. Thus, it implies that self-efficacy is associated with the stakeholders' engagement. It was found that when the level of self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 226. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value, as indicated in the table was 0.148. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.79, which led to the rejection

of the null hypothesis. The level of self-efficacy significantly influenced the level of stakeholders' engagement.

This assumption parallels to the study of Usher et al. (2019), who claim that the stakeholders' engagement, on the other hand, involves the active participation, involvement, and dedication of people or organizations with a stake in or influence over a specific project, organization, or endeavor. When the stakeholders have high levels of self-efficacy, they are more likely to be motivated and confident in their ability to contribute effectively and make a meaningful impact. Thus, this leads to increased engagement as they willingly invest their time, energy, and resources into the project or organization. Conversely, low self-efficacy can hinder stakeholders' engagement, as individuals may doubt their abilities and feel less inclined to participate and contribute actively. Therefore, fostering self-efficacy among the stakeholders can positively influence their engagement, collaboration, and commitment to shared goals and outcomes.

Significant Relationship between Stakeholders' Engagement and Learner's Motivation

Data revealed a significant relationship between stakeholders' engagement and learners' motivation. It implies that the stakeholders' engagement level is associated with the learner's motivation. It was found that when the level of stakeholders' engagement and learners' motivation were tested, the data were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a difference of 226. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value, as indicated in the table was 0.148. It was more significant than the tabular value of 0.81, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The level of stakeholder engagement significantly influenced the level of learner motivation.

This assumption parallels to the study of Handagoon and Varma (2019), who claim that the stakeholders' active engagement can significantly impact learners' motivation. By providing role models, support, relevance, collaboration, and resources, the stakeholders can create an environment that fosters intrinsic motivation, enthusiasm, and a sense of purpose to the learners. In turn, leads to increased involvement, active participation, and a more profound commitment to the learning process.

On the Mediating Effect of Stakeholders' Engagement on the Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Learners' Motivation

The data indicate significant relationships between self-efficacy, stakeholders' engagement, and learners' motivation. Self-efficacy has a robust positive effect on learners' motivation and stakeholders' engagement. Moreover, stakeholders' engagement also substantially and positively impacts learners' motivation. These findings suggest the importance of promoting self-efficacy beliefs and stakeholders' active involvement to enhance learners' motivation in the educational context. This assumption parallels to the study of Kasalak and Dagyar (2020), who claim that the underlying mechanisms by which the involvement of the stakeholders affect the connection between self-efficacy and learners' motivation. The support of the stakeholders serve as a mediating factor, enhancing the relationship between self-efficacy and motivation.

Conclusion

Based on the study results, the following conclusions were established: The level of learners' self-efficacy was high in student engagement, classroom management, and instructional strategies. The level of learners' motivation was high regarding self-motivation, intrinsic value, and cognitive strategy. Stakeholders' involvement was high in school and budgeting, learners' participation, and implementation of school programs and reforms.

Additionally, there was a significant relationship between self-efficacy and learners' motivation, self-efficacy and stakeholders' engagement, and stakeholders' engagement and learners' motivation. Moreover, self-efficacy directly affects learners' motivation and stakeholders' engagement, as well as stakeholders' engagement and learners' motivation.

The following recommendations were established based on the results: The Department of Education may provide clear guidelines and frameworks for promoting stakeholders' involvement in schools. These guidelines illustrate the importance of collaboration between teachers, parents, community members, and students to enhance self-efficacy and motivation. The school head may promote and facilitate positive stakeholder relationships, including teachers, parents, and community members. Encouraging regular communication, collaborative decision-making, and shared responsibility will create a supportive network focused on enhancing self-efficacy and motivation.

Additionally, teachers may establish positive relationships with students and parents and employ instructional strategies that enhance self-efficacy and motivation. School administrators may regularly evaluate the effectiveness of their engagement activities to ensure that they meet the stakeholders' needs. Finally, future researchers may utilize the study's findings to sharpen their research interests and abilities and serve as a guide for people who intend to perform research related to the study.

References

- Aarikka-Stenroos, L., Ritala, P., & Thomas, L. D. (2021). Circular economy ecosystems: A typology, definitions, and implications. *Research Handbook of Sustainability Agency*, 260-276. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781789906035.00024>
- Abate, S. G., & Adamu, A. Y. (2022). Stakeholders' participation in adult education programme development in Ethiopia. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2022.2052990>

- Aboramadan, M., Dahleez, K., & Hamad, M. (2020). Servant leadership and academics' engagement in higher education: Mediation analysis. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 42(6), 617-633. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2020.1774036>
- Adams, N., Little, T. D., & Ryan, R. M. (2017). Self-determination theory. Development of self-determination through the life-course, 47-54. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-94-024-1042-6_4
- Adams, D., Young, K., & Keen, D. (2019). Anxiety in children with autism at school: A systematic review. *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 6, 274-288. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40489-019-00172-z>
- Adegoke, B. O., Alumona, C. J., Adeyemo, A. A., & Adeyinka, A. O. (2021). Flatfoot and balance performance among junior secondary school students in Ibadan, Nigeria. *New Zealand Journal of Physiotherapy*, 49(2). <https://doi.org/10.15619/NZJP/49.2.04>
- Adhikari, G. P. (2021). Calculating the sample size in quantitative studies. *Scholars' Journal*, 14-29. <http://surl.li/ictkhj>
- Afzal, F., & Crawford, L. (2022). Student's perception of engagement in online project management education and its impact on performance: The mediating role of self-motivation. *Project Leadership and Society*, 3, 100057. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plas.2022.100057>
- Aggarwal, I., Woolley, A. W., Chabris, C. F., & Malone, T. W. (2019). The impact of cognitive style diversity on implicit learning in teams. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 112. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00112>
- Alam, A. (2021). Need-based perspective study of teachers' work motivation as examined from self-determination theoretical framework: An empirical investigation. Available at SSRN 3771341. <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/2213>
- Alghamdi, A., Karpinski, A. C., Lepp, A., & Barkley, J. (2020). Online and face-to-face classroom multitasking and academic performance: Moderated mediation with self-efficacy for self-regulated learning and gender. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 102, 214-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.08.018>
- Aliyyah, R. R., Rasmitadila, R., Humaira, M. A., Mujahidin, E., Suryadi, S., Widayarsi, W., & Rachmadtullah, R. (2020). Are the assessment criteria and the role of educational stakeholders able to make outstanding teacher. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*. <https://www.scienceirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S074756321930305X>
- Anderman, E. M. (2020). Achievement motivation theory: Balancing precision and utility. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101864>
- Ansley, B. M., Houchins, D., & Varjas, K. (2019). Cultivating positive work contexts that promote teacher job satisfaction and retention in high-need schools. *Journal of Special Education Leadership*, 32(1), 3-16. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1274904>
- Arnstein, S. R. (1969). A ladder of citizen participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), 216-224. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01944366908977225>
- Ashaye, O. R., & Irani, Z. (2019). The role of stakeholders in the effective use of e-government resources in public services. *International Journal of Information Management*, 49, 253-270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.05.016>
- Backfisch, I., Lachner, A., Hische, C., Loose, F., & Scheiter, K. (2020). Professional knowledge or motivation? Investigating the role of teachers' expertise on the quality of technology-enhanced lesson plans. *Learning and Instruction*, 66, 101300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2019.101300>
- Baik, C., Larcombe, W., & Brooker, A. (2019). How universities can enhance student mental wellbeing: The student perspective. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 38(4), 674-687. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/07294360.2019.1576596>
- Barney, D. C., & Leavitt, T. (2019). A qualitative investigation of PE teachers perceptions of introductory/warm-up activities in k-12 PE. *The Physical Educator*, 76(1). <https://doi.org/10.18666/TPE-2019-V76-I1-8445>
- Barni, D., Danioni, F., & Benevene, P. (2019). Teachers' self-efficacy: The role of personal values and motivations for teaching. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1645. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01645>
- Bartholomew, K. J., Ntoumanis, N., Mouratidis, A., Katartzi, E., Thøgersen-Ntoumani, C., & Vlachopoulos, S. (2018). Beware of your teaching style: A school-year long investigation of controlling teaching and student motivational experiences. *Learning and Instruction*, 53, 50-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2017.07.006>
- Bellibaş, M. Ş., Polatcan, M., & Kılınç, A. Ç. (2022). Linking instructional leadership to teacher practices: The mediating effect of shared practice and agency in learning effectiveness. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 50(5), 812-831. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1741143220945706>
- Black, J., Hashimzade, N., & Myles, G. (2012). *A dictionary of economics*. Oxford University Press, USA. <https://www.amazon.com/Dictionary-Economics-Oxford-Quick-Reference/dp/0199696322>

- Bloomfield, J., & Fisher, M. J. (2019). Quantitative research design. *Journal of the Australasian Rehabilitation Nurses Association*, 22(2), 27-30. <https://search.informit.org/doi/abs/10.3316/INFORMIT.738299924514584>
- Brandenberger, C. C., Hagenauer, G., & Hascher, T. (2018). Promoting students' self-determined motivation in maths: Results of a 1-year classroom intervention. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 33, 295-317. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10212-017-0336-y>
- Burić, I., & Kim, L. E. (2020). Teacher self-efficacy, instructional quality, and student motivational beliefs: An analysis using multilevel structural equation modeling. *Learning and Instruction*, 66, 101302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2019.101302>
- Cardullo, V., Wang, C. H., Burton, M., & Dong, J. (2021). K-12 teachers' remote teaching self-efficacy during the pandemic. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 14(1), 32-45. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/JRIT-10-2020-0055/full/html>
- Chamot, A. U., & Harris, V. (Eds.). (2019). *Learning strategy instruction in the language classroom: Issues and implementation (Vol. 132)*. Multilingual Matters. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.21832/9781788923415/html>
- Chan, K. K. H., & Hume, A. (2019). Towards a consensus model: Literature review of how science teachers' pedagogical content knowledge is investigated in empirical studies. *Repositioning Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Teachers' Knowledge for Teaching Science*, 3-76. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-13-5898-2_1
- Chen, J., & Guo, W. (2020). Emotional intelligence can make a difference: The impact of principals' emotional intelligence on teaching strategy mediated by instructional leadership. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(1), 82-105. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1741143218781066>
- Chen, L., & Xiao, S. (2021). Perceptions, challenges and coping strategies of science teachers in teaching socioscientific issues: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 32, 100377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2020.100377>
- Cheng, K. H., & Tsai, C. C. (2019). A case study of immersive virtual field trips in an elementary classroom: Students' learning experience and teacher-student interaction behaviors. *Computers & Education*, 140, 103600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103600>
- Cheng, Y. C. (2022). *School effectiveness and school-based management: A mechanism for development*. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003267980>
- Cho, M. H., & Lee, H. (2017). Understanding of e-books among undergraduate students: Uses and preferences. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange (JETDE)*, 10(2), 1-14. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/APJIE-05-2018-0028/full/html>
- Choong, Y. O., Ng, L. P., Ai Na, S., & Tan, C. E. (2020). The role of teachers' self-efficacy between trust and organisational citizenship behaviour among secondary school teachers. *Personnel Review*, 49(3), 864-886. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/PR-10-2018-0434/full/html>
- Collie, R. J., Granziera, H., & Martin, A. J. (2019). Teachers' motivational approach: Links with students' basic psychological need frustration, maladaptive engagement, and academic outcomes. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 86, 102872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.07.002>
- Conner, A. M. (2022). *Actions of the principal: Influences on teacher self-efficacy and motivation*. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/doctoral/3689/>
- Cooksey, R. W., & Cooksey, R. W. (2020). Descriptive statistics for summarising data. *Illustrating Statistical Procedures: Finding Meaning in Quantitative Data*, 61-139. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-15-2537-7_5
- Cruz, R. A., Manchanda, S., Firestone, A. R., & Rodl, J. E. (2020). An examination of teachers' culturally responsive teaching self-efficacy. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 43(3), 197-214. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0888406419875194>
- Dakhi, O., Jama, J., & Irfan, D. (2020). Blended learning: A 21st century learning model at college. *International Journal of Multi Science*, 1(08), 50-65. <https://multisciencejournal.com/index.php/ijm/article/view/92>
- Dash, S. S., & Vohra, N. (2019). The leadership of the school principal: Impact on teachers' job crafting, alienation and commitment. *Management Research Review*, 42(3), 352-369. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/MRR-11-2017-0384/full/html>
- Delfino, A. P. (2019). Student engagement and academic performance of students of Partido State University. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 15(1), n1. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1222588>
- Derbali, C., Elloumi, A., & Matoussi, F. (2017). The need to learn according to psycho-didactic approach: Self-determination and

- student's performance in physical education realm. *Creative Education*, 8(07), 1155. https://www.scirp.org/html/11-6303578_77150.htm
- Deslauriers, L., McCarty, L. S., Miller, K., Callaghan, K., & Kestin, G. (2019). Measuring actual learning versus feeling of learning in response to being actively engaged in the classroom. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(39), 19251-19257. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1821936116>
- Dignath, C., & Veenman, M. V. (2021). The role of direct strategy instruction and indirect activation of self-regulated learning—Evidence from classroom observation studies. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(2), 489-533. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10648-020-09534-0>
- Dincer, A., Yeşilyurt, S., Noels, K. A., & Vargas Lascano, D. I. (2019). Self-determination and classroom engagement of EFL learners: A mixed-methods study of the self-system model of motivational development. *Sage Open*, 9(2), 2158244019853913. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244019853913>
- Doménech-Betoret, F., Gómez-Artiga, A., Abellán-Roselló, L., & Rocabert-Beú, E. (2020). MOCSE centered on students: Validation of learning demands and teacher support scales. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 582926. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.582926/full>
- Dorney, Z. (2020). *Innovations and challenges in language learning motivation*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429485893>
- Duman, İ., Horzum, M. B., & Randler, C. (2020). Adaptation of the short form of the intrinsic motivation inventory to Turkish. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 7(3), 26-33. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/pep/issue/56971/802000>
- Dweck, C. S., & Yeager, D. S. (2019). Mindsets: A view from two eras. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 14(3), 481-496. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1745691618804166>
- Engels, D., Haupt, C., Kugelmann, D., & Dethleffsen, K. (2021). The peer teachers' perception of intrinsic motivation and rewards. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 45(4), 758-768. <https://journals.physiology.org/doi/full/10.1152/advan.00023.2021>
- Engin, G. (2020). An examination of primary school students' academic achievements and motivation in terms of parents' attitudes, teacher motivation, teacher self-efficacy and leadership Approach. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 16(1), 257-276. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1244883>
- Ennis, C. D. (2017). Educating students for a lifetime of physical activity: Enhancing mindfulness, motivation, and meaning. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 88(3), 241-250. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02701367.2017.1342495>
- Epstein, J. L. (2018). School, family, and community partnerships in teachers' professional work. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 44(3), 397-406. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02607476.2018.1465669>
- Erdemir, N., & Ekşi, G. Y. (2019). The perceptions of student teachers about using an online learning environment 'Edmodo' in a 'flipped classroom'. *SDU International Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(2), 174-186. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/sduijes/issue/50325/638795>
- Esra, M. E. Ş. E., & Sevilen, Ç. (2021). Factors influencing EFL students' motivation in online learning: A qualitative case study. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 4(1), 11-22. https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/jetol/issue/60134/817680?utm_medium=email&utm_source=transaction
- Falqueto, J. M. Z., Hoffmann, V. E., Gomes, R. C., & Onoyama Mori, S. S. (2020). Strategic planning in higher education institutions: What are the stakeholders' roles in the process?. *Higher Education*, 79, 1039-1056. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10734-019-00455-8>
- Fathi, J., & Derakhshan, A. (2019). Teacher self-efficacy and emotional regulation as predictors of teaching stress: An investigation of Iranian English language teachers. *Teaching English Language*, 13(2), 117-143. https://www.teljournal.org/article_95883.html
- Ferrero-Ferrero, I., Fernández-Izquierdo, M. Á., Muñoz-Torres, M. J., & Bellés-Colomer, L. (2018). Stakeholder engagement in sustainability reporting in higher education: An analysis of key internal stakeholders' expectations. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 19(2), 313-336. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJSHE-06-2016-0116/full/html>
- Fishbach, A., & Woolley, K. (2022). The structure of intrinsic motivation. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology*, 73, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012420-091122>
- Fithriani, R. (2021). The utilization of mobile-assisted gamification for vocabulary learning. <http://repository.uinsu.ac.id/id/eprint/18265>
- Franklin, H., & Harrington, I. (2019). A review into effective classroom management and strategies for student engagement: Teacher

- and student roles in today's classrooms. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v7i12.4491>
- Fredricks, J. A., Reschly, A. L., & Christenson, S. L. (2019). Interventions for student engagement: Overview and state of the field. *Handbook of Student Engagement Interventions*, 1-11. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780128134139000012>
- Freeman, R (2017). The relationship between extracurricular activities and academic achievement dissertations. <https://digitalcommons.nl.edu/diss/245>
- Gaias, L. M., Johnson, S. L., Bottiani, J. H., Debnam, K. J., & Bradshaw, C. P. (2019). Examining teachers' classroom management profiles: Incorporating a focus on culturally responsive practice. *Journal of School Psychology*, 76, 124-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2019.07.017>
- Geng, Y., Cheung, S. P., Huang, C. C., & Liao, J. (2022). Volunteering among Chinese College Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9), 5154. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19095154>
- Georgii-Hemming, E., Johansson, K., & Moberg, N. (2020). Reflection in higher music education: What, why, wherefore?. *Music Education Research*, 22(3), 245-256. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14613808.2020.1766006>
- Goldberg, P., Sümer, Ö., Stürmer, K., Wagner, W., Göllner, R., Gerjets, P. & Trautwein, U. (2021). Attentive or not? Toward a machine learning approach to assessing students' visible engagement in classroom instruction. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33, 27-49. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10648-019-09514-z>
- Gonzalez-DeHass, A. R. (2019). Self-regulated learning: How parents can help children take personal responsibility for their learning. In *Parent Involvement for Motivated Learners* (pp. 83-103). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781351021906-5/self-regulated-learning-alyssa-gonzalez-dehass>
- Granziera, H., & Perera, H. N. (2019). Relations among teachers' self-efficacy beliefs, engagement, and work satisfaction: A social cognitive view. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 58, 75-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2019.02.003>
- Grillo, M., & Kier, M. (2021). Why do they stay? An exploratory analysis of identities and commitment factors associated with teaching retention in high-need school contexts. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 105, 103423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103423>
- Guay, F., Roy, A., & Valois, P. (2017). Teacher structure as a predictor of students' perceived competence and autonomous motivation: The moderating role of differentiated instruction. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 87(2), 224-240. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12146>
- Gustanti, Y., & Ayu, M. (2021). The correlation between cognitive reading strategies and students' English proficiency test score. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 2(2), 95-100. <https://jim.teknokrat.ac.id/index.php/english-language-teaching/article/view/1452>
- Hajovsky, D. B., Chesnut, S. R., & Jensen, K. M. (2020). The role of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the development of teacher-student relationships. *Journal of School Psychology*, 82, 141-158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2020.09.001>
- Halik, A., Hanafie Das, S. W., Dangnga, M. S., Rady, M., Aswad, M., & Nasir, M. (2019). Empowerment of school committee in improving education service quality at public primary school in Parepare City. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(9), 1956-1963. <https://repository.iainpare.ac.id/id/eprint/1064/>
- Handagoon, S., & Varma, P. (2019). The Influence of social support and student's self efficacy on academic engagement of undergraduate students mediated by sense of belonging and psychological distress. *Scholar: Human Sciences*, 11(2), 135-135. <http://www.assumptionjournal.au.edu/index.php/Scholar/article/view/3438>
- Havik, T., & Westergård, E. (2020). Do teachers matter? Students' perceptions of classroom interactions and student engagement. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 64(4), 488-507. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2019.1577754>
- Hepburn, L., Beamish, W., & Alston-Knox, C. L. (2021). Classroom management practices commonly used by secondary school teachers: Results from a Queensland survey. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 48(3), 485-505. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13384-020-00402-y>
- Hill, N. E., Witherspoon, D. P., & Bartz, D. (2018). Parental involvement in education during middle school: Perspectives of ethnically diverse parents, teachers, and students. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 111(1), 12-27. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00220671.2016.1190910>
- Hiver, P., Al-Hoorie, A. H., & Mercer, S. (Eds.). (2020). Student engagement in the language classroom (Vol. 11). *Multilingual Matters*. <https://www.amazon.com/Engagement-Language-Classroom-Psychology-Learning/dp/1788923596>
- Holzberger, D., & Prestele, E. (2021). Teacher self-efficacy and self-reported cognitive activation and classroom management: A

- multilevel perspective on the role of school characteristics. *Learning and Instruction*, 76, 101513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2021.101513>
- Hsu, C.-L., & Ching, Y.-H. (2018). The effects of social media on college students. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 11(1), 1-14. https://scholarsarchive.jwu.edu/mba_student/5/
- Hu, M., & Li, H. (2017). Student engagement in online learning: A review. In 2017 International Symposium on Educational Technology (ISET) (pp. 39-43). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISET.2017.17>
- Huyer, L. D., Callaghan, N. I., Dicks, S., Scherer, E., Shukalyuk, A. I., Jou, M., & Kilkenny, D. M. (2020). Enhancing senior high school student engagement and academic performance using an inclusive and scalable inquiry-based program. *Npj Science of Learning*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41539-020-00076-2>
- Igwenagu, C. (2016). *Fundamentals of research methodology and data collection*. LAP Lambert Academic Publishing. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303381524>
- Ismail, I. A., Pernadi, N. L., & Febriyanti, A. (2022). How to grab and determine the size of the sample for research. *International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR)*, 6(9), 88-92. <http://repository.unp.ac.id/41155/>
- Jabri, U., Elihami, E., & Ibrahim, I. (2019). The effects of approach instruction on student's reading performance. *Jurnal Edukasi Nonformal*, 1(1), 72-80. <https://ummaspul.e-journal.id/JENFOL/article/view/191>
- Jongbloed, B., Enders, J., & Salerno, C. (2008). Higher education and its communities: Interconnections, interdependencies and a research agenda. *Higher Education*, 56, 303-324. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-008-9128-2>
- Kasalak, G., & Dagyar, M. (2020). The relationship between teacher self-efficacy and teacher job satisfaction: A meta-analysis of the teaching and learning international survey (TALIS). *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 20(3), 16-33. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1261816>
- Katemiadi, I., & Markatos, G. (2021). Stakeholders' involvement in sustainability planning and implementation: The case of Cyprus. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/WHATT-07-2021-0095/full/html>
- Katsantonis, I. G. (2019). Investigation of the impact of school climate and teachers' self-efficacy on job satisfaction: A cross-cultural approach. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 10(1), 119-133. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe10010011>
- Khan, A., Egbue, O., Palkie, B., & Madden, J. (2017). Active learning: Engaging students to maximize learning in an online course. *Electronic Journal of e-learning*, 15(2), pp107-115. <https://academic-publishing.org/index.php/ejel/article/view/1824>
- Khan, T., Johnston, K., & Ophoff, J. (2019). The impact of an augmented reality application on learning motivation of students. *Advances in Human-Computer Interaction*, 2019. <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/ahci/2019/7208494/>
- Kelley, T. R., Knowles, J. G., Holland, J. D., & Han, J. (2020). Increasing high school teachers self-efficacy for integrated STEM instruction through a collaborative community of practice. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7, 1-13. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40594-020-00211-w>
- Knoke, D. (1999). Organizational networks and corporate social capital. In *Corporate Social Capital and Liability*. Boston, MA: Springer US. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4615-5027-3_2
- Krause, T. M., Ganduglia-Cazaban, C., Piller, L. B., & Venkataraman, V. (2018). Comparison of utilization of urgent care and primary care 2011-2015. *Future Med Chem*, 1(1), 1-2. <https://www.oatext.com/comparison-of-utilization-of-urgent-care-and-primary-care-2011-2015.php>
- Kujala, J., Sachs, S., Leinonen, H., Heikkinen, A., & Laude, D. (2022). Stakeholder engagement: Past, present, and future. *Business & Society*, 00076503211066595. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/00076503211066595>
- Kwok, A. (2021). Pre-service teachers' classroom management beliefs and associated teacher characteristics. *Educational Studies*, 47(5), 609-626. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03055698.2020.1717932>
- Kwon, K., Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T., Sari, A. R., Khlaif, Z., Zhu, M., Nadir, H., & Gok, F. (2019). Teachers' self-efficacy matters: Exploring the integration of mobile computing device in middle schools. *TechTrends*, 63, 682-692. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11528-019-00402-5>
- Lai, Y., Saab, N., & Admiraal, W. (2022). Learning strategies in self-directed language learning using mobile technology in higher education: A systematic scoping review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(6), 7749-7780. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-022-10945-5>

- Lamon, S. J. (2020). Teaching fractions and ratios for understanding: Essential content knowledge and instructional strategies for teachers. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003008057>
- Lathifah, Z. K., Helmanto, F., & Maryani, N. (2020). The practice of effective classroom management in COVID-19 time. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(7), 3263-3271. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Fachri-Helmanto-2/publication/346649659_The_Practice_of_Effective_Classroom_Management_in_COVID-19_Time/links/5fcb922e299bf188d4f6f109/The-Practice-of-Effective-Classroom-Management-in-COVID-19-Time.pdf
- Lazarides, R., Watt, H. M., & Richardson, P. W. (2020). Teachers' classroom management self-efficacy, perceived classroom management and teaching contexts from beginning until mid-career. *Learning and Instruction*, 69, 101346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2020.101346>
- Lepper, M. R., & Malone, T. W. (2021). Intrinsic motivation and instructional effectiveness in computer-based education. In *Aptitude, learning, and instruction* (pp. 255-286). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781003163244-11/intrinsic-motivation-instructional-effectiveness-computer-based-education-mark-lepper-thomas-malone>
- MacDonald, A., Clarke, A., Huang, L., & Seitanidi, M. M. (2019). Partner strategic capabilities for capturing value from sustainability-focused multi-stakeholder partnerships. *Sustainability*, 11(3), 557. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11030557>
- Maier, A., Daniel, J., Oakes, J., & Lam, L. (2017). Community schools as an effective school improvement strategy: A review of the evidence. Learning Policy Institute. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED606765>
- Manwaring, K. C., Larsen, R., Graham, C. R., Henrie, C. R., & Halverson, L. R. (2017). Investigating student engagement in blended learning settings using experience sampling and structural equation modeling. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 35, 21-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.06.002>
- Marks, G. N., & O'Connell, M. (2021). Inadequacies in the SES–Achievement model: Evidence from PISA and other studies. *Review of Education*, 9(3), e3293. <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/rev3.3293>
- Marshall, S. J. (2018). Internal and external stakeholders in higher education. In *Shaping the University of the Future*. Springer, Singapore. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-981-10-7620-6>
- Marshman, E. M., Kalender, Z. Y., Nokes-Malach, T., Schunn, C., & Singh, C. (2018). Female students with A's have similar physics self-efficacy as male students with C's in introductory courses: A cause for alarm?. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 14(2), 020123. <https://journals.aps.org/prper/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevPhysEducRes.14.020123>
- Martin, M. (2019). The implementation of school-based management in public elementary schools. *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, 9(1), 44-56. <https://doi.org/10.37134/ajatel.vol9.no1.5.2019>
- McCowan, T. (2019). Higher education for and beyond the sustainable development goals. Springer Nature. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-19597-7>
- McDougle, S. D., & Taylor, J. A. (2019). Dissociable cognitive strategies for sensorimotor learning. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 40. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-018-07941-0>
- Morais, P., Ferreira, M. J., & Veloso, B. (2021). Improving student engagement with Project-Based Learning: A case study in Software Engineering. *IEEE Revista Iberoamericana de Tecnologías del Aprendizaje*, 16(1), 21-28. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RITA.2021.3052677>
- Moşteanu, N. R. (2021). Teaching and learning techniques for the online environment. how to maintain students' attention and achieve learning outcomes in a virtual environment using new technology. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 4(4), 278-290. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9328311>
- Murillo-Zamorano, L. R., Sánchez, J. Á. L., & Godoy-Caballero, A. L. (2019). How the flipped classroom affects knowledge, skills, and engagement in higher education: Effects on students' satisfaction. *Computers & Education*, 141, 103608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103608>
- Myers, D., Freeman, J., Simonsen, B., & Sugai, G. (2017). Classroom management with exceptional learners. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 49(4), 223-230. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0040059916685064>
- Nahapiet, J., & Ghoshal, S. (1998). Social capital, intellectual capital, and the organizational advantage. *Academy of Management Review*, 23(2), 242-266. <https://journals.aom.org/doi/abs/10.5465/amr.1998.533225>
- Nappi, J. S. (2017). The importance of questioning in developing critical thinking skills. *Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin*, 84(1), 30. https://www.dkg.is/static/files/skjol_landsamband/bulletin_grein_jona.pdf#page=30
- Nasr, A. K., Kashan, M. K., Maleki, A., Jafari, N., & Hashemi, H. (2020). Assessment of barriers to renewable energy development using stakeholders approach. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 7(3), 2526. [http://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.7.3\(71\)](http://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.7.3(71))

- Nurlisa, N., Sada, C., & Ikhsanudin, I. (2020). Improving students' engagement using scaffolded role play and Facebook discussion. *Journal of English as a Foreign Language Education (JEFLE)*, 1(2), 31-39. <https://jurnal.untan.ac.id/index.php/JEFLE/article/view/43749>
- Osman, D. J., & Warner, J. R. (2020). Measuring teacher motivation: The missing link between professional development and practice. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 92, 103064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103064>
- Özdemir, N. (2019). Principal leadership and students' achievement: Mediated pathways of professional community and teachers' instructional practices. *KEDI Journal of Educational Policy*, 16(1). <http://surl.li/olxtjw>
- Panadero, E., Jonsson, A., & Botella, J. (2017). Effects of self-assessment on self-regulated learning and self-efficacy: Four meta-analyses. *Educational Research Review*, 22, 74-98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2017.08.004>
- Patall, E. A., Pituch, K. A., Steingut, R. R., Vasquez, A. C., Yates, N., & Kennedy, A. A. (2019). Agency and high school science students' motivation, engagement, and classroom support experiences. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 62, 77-92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2019.01.004>
- Pelikan, E. R., Lüftenegger, M., Holzer, J., Korlat, S., Spiel, C., & Schober, B. (2021). Learning during COVID-19: The role of self-regulated learning, motivation, and procrastination for perceived competence. *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft*, 24(2), 393-418. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11618-021-01002-x>
- Perera, H. N., Calkins, C., & Part, R. (2019). Teacher self-efficacy profiles: Determinants, outcomes, and generalizability across teaching level. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 58, 186-203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2019.02.006>
- Perera, H. N., & John, J. E. (2020). Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs for teaching math: Relations with teacher and student outcomes. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101842>
- Pintrich, P. R., & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.82.1.33>
- Pressley, T., & Ha, C. (2021). Teaching during a pandemic: United States teachers' self-efficacy during COVID-19. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 106, 103465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103465>
- Puspitarini, Y. D., & Hanif, M. (2019). Using learning media to increase learning motivation in elementary school. *Anatolian Journal of Education*, 4(2), 53-60. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ej1244451>
- Raes, A., Vanneste, P., Pieters, M., Windey, I., Van Den Noortgate, W., & Depaep, F. (2020). Learning and instruction in the hybrid virtual classroom: An investigation of students' engagement and the effect of quizzes. *Computers & Education*, 143, 103682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103682>
- Rafiola, R., Setyosari, P., Radjah, C., & Ramli, M. (2020). The effect of learning motivation, self-efficacy, and blended learning on students' achievement in the industrial revolution 4.0. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 15(8), 71-82. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/217073/>
- Rahman, M. S. (2020). The advantages and disadvantages of using qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods in language "testing and assessment" research: A literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v6n1p102>
- Rasmitadila, R., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., Tambunan, A., Khairas, E., & Nurtanto, M. (2020). The Benefits of Implementation of an Instructional Strategy Model Based on the Brain's Natural Learning Systems in Inclusive Classrooms in Higher Education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 15(18), 53-72. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/217880/>
- Ray, K. N., & Miller, E. (2017). Strengthening stakeholder-engaged research and research on stakeholder engagement. *Journal of Comparative Effectiveness Research*, 6(4), 375-389. <https://becarispublishing.com/doi/full/10.2217/cer-2016-0096>
- Reckwitz, A. (2020). The society of singularities. <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Society-Singularities-Andreas-Reckwitz/dp/1509534229>
- Reeve, J., & Cheon, S. H. (2021). Autonomy-supportive teaching: Its malleability, benefits, and potential to improve educational practice. *Educational Psychologist*, 56(1), 54-77. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00461520.2020.1862657>
- Reeve, J., & Shin, S. H. (2020). How teachers can support students' agentic engagement. *Theory Into Practice*, 59(2), 150-161. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00405841.2019.1702451>
- Rudo, Z., & Dimock, V. (2017). How family, school, and community engagement can improve student achievement and influence school reform. <http://surl.li/nkhcim>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>

- Ryan, R. M., & Rigby, C. S. (2019). Motivational foundations of game-based learning. *Handbook of game-based learning*, 153-176. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2020-10545-006>
- Salvioni, D. M., Franzoni, S., & Cassano, R. (2017). Sustainability in the higher education system: An opportunity to improve quality and image. *Sustainability*, 9(6), 914. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9060914>
- Savga, L., Kryklyi, O., & Kyrychenko, K. (2018). The role of internal and external stakeholders in higher education system in Ukraine. *Business Ethics and Leadership*, 2(1), 32-43. [https://doi.org/10.21272/bel.2\(1\).32-43.2018](https://doi.org/10.21272/bel.2(1).32-43.2018)
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2021). Self-efficacy and human motivation. In *Advances in Motivation Science* (Vol. 8, pp. 153-179). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.adms.2020.10.001>
- Seeram, E. (2021). Quantitative and qualitative research: An overview of approaches. *Research for Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences*, 13-23. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-79956-4_2
- Seneviratne, K., Hamid, J. A., Khatibi, A., Azam, F., & Sudasinghe, S. (2019). Multi-faceted professional development designs for science teachers' self-efficacy for inquiry-based teaching: A critical review. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(7), 1595-1611. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2019.070714>
- Shin, M. H. (2018). Effects of project-based learning on students' motivation and self-efficacy. *English Teaching*, 73(1), 95-114. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1312282.pdf>
- Siedlecki, S. L. (2020). Understanding descriptive research designs and methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), 8-12. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493>
- Slemp, G. R., Field, J. G., & Cho, A. S. (2020). A meta-analysis of autonomous and controlled forms of teacher motivation. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 121, 103459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2020.103459>
- Sprick, J., Sprick, R., Edwards, J., & Coughlin, C. (2021). CHAMPS: A proactive & positive approach to classroom management. *Safe & Civil Schools*. Ancora Publishing. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED615489>
- Struyf, A., De Loof, H., Boeve-de Pauw, J., & Van Petegem, P. (2019). Students' engagement in different STEM learning environments: Integrated STEM education as promising practice?. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(10), 1387-1407. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09500693.2019.1607983>
- Swart, L. A., Kramer, S., Ratele, K., & Seedat, M. (2019). 2 Non-experimental research designs: Investigating the spatial distribution and social ecology of male homicide. *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*, 19, 19. <https://doi.org/10.18772/22019032750.7>
- Syarifuddin, H., & Atweh, B. (2022). The use of activity, classroom discussion, and exercise (ACE) Teaching cycle for improving students' engagement in learning elementary linear algebra. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 10(1), 104-138. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1329228>
- Talan, T., & Gulsecen, S. (2019). The effect of a flipped classroom on students' achievements, academic engagement and satisfaction levels. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 20(4), 31-60. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/tojde/article/640503>
- Tokan, M. K., & Imakulata, M. M. (2019). The effect of motivation and learning behaviour on student achievement. *South African Journal of Education*, 39(1). DOI:10.15700/saje.v39n1a1510
- Tomas, L., Evans, N. S., Doyle, T., & Skamp, K. (2019). Are first year students ready for a flipped classroom? A case for a flipped learning continuum. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 1-22. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s41239-019-0135-4>
- Usher, E. L., Li, C. R., Butz, A. R., & Rojas, J. P. (2019). Perseverant grit and self-efficacy: Are both essential for children's academic success?. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(5), 877. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000324>
- Van den Branden, K. (2019). *Rethinking schools and renewing energy for learning: Research, principles and practice*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351044318>
- Viennet, R., & Pont, B. (2017). Education policy implementation: A literature review and proposed framework. <https://doi.org/10.1787/19939019>
- Vollet, J. W., Kindermann, T. A., & Skinner, E. A. (2017). In peer matters, teachers matter: Peer group influences on students' engagement depend on teacher involvement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 109(5), 635. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000172>
- Vong, S. A., & Kaewurai, W. (2017). Instructional model development to enhance critical thinking and critical thinking teaching ability of trainee students at regional teaching training center in Takeo province, Cambodia. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 38(1), 88-95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjss.2016.05.002>

Wigfield, A., & Eccles, J. S. (2020). 35 years of research on students' subjective task values and motivation: A look back and a look forward. In *Advances in motivation science* (Vol. 7, pp. 161-198). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.adms.2019.05.002>

Wolff, C. E., Jarodzka, H., & Boshuizen, H. P. (2021). Classroom management scripts: A theoretical model contrasting expert and novice teachers' knowledge and awareness of classroom events. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33, 131-148. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10648-020-09542-0>

Yada, A., Tolvanen, A., Malinen, O. P., Imai-Matsumura, K., Shimada, H., Koike, R., & Savolainen, H. (2019). Teachers' self-efficacy and the sources of efficacy: A cross-cultural investigation in Japan and Finland. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 81, 13-24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.01.014>

Zainuddin, Z., Haruna, H., Li, X., Zhang, Y., & Chu, S. K. W. (2019). A systematic review of flipped classroom empirical evidence from different fields: what are the gaps and future trends?. On the horizon. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/OTH-09-2018-0027/full/html>

Zhang, S., & Liu, Q. (2019). Investigating the relationships among teachers' motivational beliefs, motivational regulation, and their learning engagement in online professional learning communities. *Computers & Education*, 134, 145-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.02.013>

Zarouk, M., Olivera, E., Peres, P., & Khaldi, M. (2020). The impact of flipped project-based learning on self-regulation in higher education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 15(17), 127-147. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/218014/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Estorina B. Tugade

Department of Education – Philippines

Lyndon A. Quines

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines

Geraldine D. Rodriguez

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines